

MATERIAL-CULTURAL SAMPLES OF WESTERN AZERBAIJAN AS A HISTORICAL SOURCE**Ismayilova A. V¹.****Abbasova S.H².**<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4507-994X><https://orcid.org/0009-0001-1528-0151>**Abstract**

In the territory of Western Azerbaijan, there are rock paintings, temples, mosques, bridges, etc., among the material and cultural heritage of the Azerbaijani people. Each of these monuments is a historical source that carries traces of the history of Azerbaijan. There is information about the historical monuments and material and cultural samples found here in written sources from various periods - travelers' diaries, reports, political documents, etc. As a result, it is possible to clarify information about the period, character, and main features of historical monuments. Historical monuments of Western Azerbaijan are falsified by Armenians and presented as their own, and most of them were destroyed in order to erase our historical traces. However, the study of these monuments and their comparative analysis with information obtained from various written sources and historical documents once again show that the territory of Western Azerbaijan is the historical land of the Azerbaijani people and Azerbaijanis were forcibly and purposefully deported from their native places. The article provides information about the currently destroyed and destroyed monuments based on sources from various periods. It is emphasized here once again that historical monuments carry a lot of information about the past. Regardless of the reason, the destruction of historical monuments is unacceptable and it is important to protect them as universal values.

Keywords: Western Azerbaijan, Iravan Yerevan, Zangezur, historical monuments, protection of monuments, historical source

This work was supported by the Azerbaijan Science Foundation – Grant № AEF-GAT-7-2023-2(44)-10/10/5-M-10

Introduction. Architectural monuments, material and cultural artifacts provide information about the past - ancient periods of history. Material and cultural artifacts found in various areas provide information about the history of that region, the people who lived there and created the monument. The issue of using the material that has remained in the past as a source of information is still relevant today. Various material and historical information is obtained from material sources. When researching and analyzing material culture, it is also necessary to refer to written sources of the period. It is possible to find information about its monuments, residential complexes, religious buildings - mosques, temples, etc., which is recorded in many places. It is important to thoroughly study the archaeological source, the monuments themselves. A complex analysis of historical objectivity calculations is important. However, it should be strictly noted that the monuments discovered in all areas are analyzed in accordance with the historical movement, as well as destroyed for any object. In addition to the correct and impartial use of monuments that convey various information to us, the protection of historical monuments is as important as the protection of world cultural heritage. Therefore, decisions have been made at the international level regarding the protection of historical monuments. UNESCO focuses on this work, and in 1965, ICOMOS ICOMOS international council on monuments and sites was established. Based on the proposal of ICOMOS, a decision was made by UNESCO in 1983. According to this decision, April 18 is celebrated as the International Day For Monuments

and Sites (ICOMOS international council on monuments and sites).

Most countries of the world cooperate with UNESCO in the protection of monuments. A number of decisions have also been made in local legislation in this regard. But the problem is that the states that have undertaken the obligation not only do not always comply with the protection of historical monuments, but also carry out the destruction of these monuments. Since the 1990s, theoretical and methodological research in the archaeology of the post-Soviet space, including the analysis of archaeological materials as historical sources, has been stagnant, with rare exceptions, and discussions are few (Kariev, E.M. & Samratova D.B., 2021, p.77). Taking all this into account, this research study aims to investigate the role of historical monuments located in the lands of Western Azerbaijan, now called the territory of Armenia, as sources, and the current state of these monuments.

Study of Western Azerbaijan from an archaeological perspective. Our material and cultural heritage located in the territory of Western Azerbaijan - rock carvings, stone inscriptions, mosques, fortresses, bridges, etc. Each of the historical monuments reflects historical information. The historical monuments located here and the information about these monuments recorded in works and documents of various periods reflect historical reality. Stone inscriptions, monuments, and material and cultural samples discovered in the territory of Western Azerbaijan indicate that these territories belonged to the Azerbaijani Turks. Also, historical monuments were described in written sources of various periods, and information about them and the population was given. This information coincides with the descriptions and inscriptions on the stone inscriptions.

¹ Ismayilova Aygun Vilayat – phd Student of Baku State University, lecturer of Baku Eurasian University

² Abbasova Sevinc Hikmat – phd Student of Baku State University, lecturer of Azerbaijan University Languages

The territory of Western Azerbaijan began to be systematically studied from an archaeological point of view in the 70s-90s of the 19th century. In October 1871, the Caucasian Archaeological Committee was established in Tbilisi. From the following year, the members of this organization, called the Society of Amateurs of Caucasian Archaeology, conducted various archaeological research in the territory of Western Azerbaijan. In 1880, archaeologist Uvarov, who visited Iravan, also reported on the Iravan fortress and the mosque located there (Huseynova, S., 8 January, 2014). He indicated that he considered the Blue Mosque in Iravan to be one of the best examples of muslim architecture. This mosque is currently presented by Armenians as a Persian cultural monument (European Charter for Regional or Minority Languages, 2007). As a result of archaeological research conducted around Lake Goycha by A. Ivanovsky, a member of the Moscow Archaeological Society, various material samples were discovered, including various graves belonging to the Oghuz Turks.

Archaeological research in Western Azerbaijan was also conducted during the years of Soviet rule. However, the material and cultural samples obtained during archaeological research conducted by the Armenian SSR were presented in museums, press and scientific literature as Armenian monuments. Not content with this, they artificially changed the discovered historical monuments. However, the fact that these material sources obtained, their unique characteristics, and the fact that they are identical and similar to monuments found in other areas once again exposes armenian lies.

As a result of archaeological excavations carried out in the 60s of the 20th century, graves dating back to the 3rd-2nd millennium BC were discovered in the village of Agkilsa in the Goycha district. These graves were mentioned in the literature as Uguz, that is, Oghuz graves. In the 70s of the last century, burial mounds were found by Armenian archaeologists in the territory of the village of Agtala. Some of the items found in these mounds, which date back to the 3rd-2nd centuries BC, are presented as Armenian specimens in Armenian museums. Such mound-type graves have also been found in the village of Ashagi Zaghali. The mounds found here date back to the 1st millennium BC. Archaeological excavations were carried out by E. Lalayan in the Ashagi Zagali mounds at the beginning of the 20th century. It should be noted that B. Piotrovsky studied the monuments and objects found here. He stated that these mounds are identical to the archaeological excavations found in other areas of Azerbaijan by A. Ivanovsky and V. Belkin (Huseynova, S., 8 January, 2014).

In the Middle Ages, as in other parts of Azerbaijan, the diaries of European travelers who visited the lands of Western Azerbaijan also reflected information about the fortresses, mosques, historical geography of the area and population. In 1655, one of the European travelers, Jean Batis Tavernier, came to Iravan. In his diary, it was noted in the information about the Iravan fortress that the population of this place was muslims (Mustafa, N., 2020, p.199). Later,

the french traveler Jean Chardin described the palace of the Sardar in his notes and stated that the population was composed of muslims. He also wrote in his notes that the walls of the fortress were irrigated by the Kirkbulag and Zangi rivers. The etymology of these names once again proves the historical truths. Evliya Chelebi, one of the travelers of the time, also provided information about the Iravan fortress. He wrote in his "Travelogue": "...in the year 915 AH (1509-10), Shah Ismail gave instructions to his vizier Ravangulu Khan to build a fortress there. He built a fortress there for 7 years and named it "Ravan". It is a strong, beautiful fortress built of stones and bricks, located on the eastern bank of the Zangi river, but it has no fence" (Evliya Chelebi seyahetnamesinde Azerbaijan, 2012, p.87; Bayramov, I, 2024, p.125).

Various historical monuments in Western Azerbaijan. Among the material and cultural examples in the territory of Western Azerbaijan, there are various monuments covering a chronological framework from the most ancient period to the modern era. These include archaeological monuments, tombstones, various castles, mosques, domes, bridges, stone inscriptions and rock paintings. One of these monuments is a cave from one of the ancient settlements located in the Bazarchay valley. This cave, which dates back to the 2nd-1st millennia BC, is considered one of the oldest settlements. Unfortunately, part of the cave was destroyed by Armenians, who tried to artificially armenize it and present it as an Armenian monument. One of the archaeological monuments located in Western Azerbaijan is the monument located in the village of Shishgaya in the Goycha district. There is an Albanian monument here, which later became a religious shrine. Various types of stones and an Albanian cross are depicted on Albanian monuments (Alakbarli A., & Valiyev A., 2021, v.I p.172).

One of the material examples reflecting historical truths is rock carvings. Examples of such carvings dating back to the 5th-2nd millennia BC include the rock carvings of Soyukbulag and Garakils. Animals and hunting-related carvings located in the Garakils district of Zangezur district predominate in the rock carvings (Sisian (spravochnik-putevoditel), 1987, p.111-112). It should be noted that these images are similar to the images on the monuments located in Gobustan. There are also images from the most ancient period on the monuments located in the Soyukbulag village of Loru district. The Soyukbulag rock carvings are almost identical to the monuments discovered in the territory of the High Altai. The similarity of these rock carvings with the monuments discovered in the Altai territory and the Gobustan images once again proves that the oldest inhabitants of these territories were Azerbaijani Turks. One of the historical monuments located in the Garakils territory is the Goshundash monument dating back to the Neolithic period. The origin of the name of the monument also provides information about the people to whom it belongs. It is no coincidence that Armenians are trying to appropriate this monument by calling it "Zorakarer". (Alakbarli, A., 2007, p.22-23).

The Gargadashi inscriptions located in the village of Nuvedi are attributed to the gargar turks. The inscriptions in Goyturk letters on this monument once again prove that they belong to the ancient Turkic people. The Urud fortress located in the Zangezur territory is one of the important material and historical monuments for studying the history of Western Azerbaijan. Information about this fortress is mentioned in the sources in the events dating back to 450. In addition to the Urud fortress, there are also historical cemeteries here. This cemetery was studied by A. Alekperov in 1926. Chest-type graves belonging to the ancient Turks are considered rare historical monuments (Musa, U., 2005 p. 31). There are also graves with images and statues of rams here. Images and statues of rams are also found in other areas, such as Nakhchivan, Lerik, and other areas. This once again shows that these monuments belong to our people. On one of the graves, it is written in Arabic: "Allah, Muhammad, Ali. Amrugal the son of the village chief, a descendant of Ali Ugvan (agvan), Ramadan month, 883" (Alakbarli, A., 2007, p.35). The inscriptions and images on the Urud monuments dating back to the Middle Ages also prove once again that this place belongs to the Azerbaijani people. Let us note that one of the scientists who conducted research here in 1961 was M. Nematova. She studied most of the historical monuments (Musa, U., 2005, p.28).

There are also ram statues in the Kosanli and Paskili cemeteries located in the Vedibasars district (Shopen, N., 1852, p. 375-378). However, this historical monument was destroyed after the deportation of Azerbaijanis that began in 1948. Armenians applied the vandalism they carried out against other monuments here to erase traces of Azerbaijanis. Such ram and horse-headed statues and images are also found in the Shidli cemetery (Alakbarli A., 2007, p. 23). Shidli is one of the villages located in the Vedi district. The name of the village originated from the ancient Turkic title of shad. This was also reported in Musa Kalankatlis work "Albanian History" (Kalankatuklu M. p. 30). There were statues called Kochdashi and Atdashi here, based on their depictions. There are also such gravestone statues in Zangibasars, in the area of the village of Gabakhli in the Daralayaz district. This is one of the indications that the depictions of horses and rams belonging to the turks here are Oghuz-Turkic lands.

Religious and cultural monuments. During the Soviet rule, in the 60s of the 20th century, Albanian monuments were found in the Goycha district, in the Narimanli village of the Basarkechar district. This monument is an Albanian monument dating back to the 2nd-1st millennium BC. In the 1970s, an Albanian temple was discovered in the village of Ardanish in the Goycha district. Considered to be the remains of an Albanian church, there were stone inscriptions on a part of this historical monument. These inscriptions were carved in ancient Turkic language (Alakbarli A., & Valiyev A., 2021, v.I p.110). One of these Albanian temples was discovered in the village of Aldara in the Zangezur region. There were also remains of many historical buildings around the temple. Since it bears

the historical traces of Azerbaijan, the monument has not been repaired, has remained neglected, and its surroundings have become a ruin. It should be noted that our compatriots, who were residents of the village, were deported in November 1988, and all Azerbaijanis were expelled from here. In the territory of the Gamarli district, around the village of Bayburt, there was an Albanian temple dating back to the 12th-13th centuries. This temple was described by the Armenians as their national-religious monument (Alakbarli A., & Valiyev A., 2021, v.I p.111). However, as the name of the village suggests, the Bayburts were one of the Turkic tribes. It is also known from written sources that there were Bayburts among the Qizilbash tribes during the Safavid period. One of such Albanian temples is the Safiya Temple, built in 936. This temple is located in the Gindivaz village of the Deralayaz district. Therefore, in some sources it is also called the Gindivaz Temple. Albanian temples are also located in the villages of Gafan, Zod, and Yukhari Kilsa. However, it is presented as an Armenian monument by Armenian scientific institutions (Alakbarli A., & Valiyev A., 2021, v.I p.117).

Among the material sources in Western Azerbaijan, there are also religious and cultural monuments - mosques, tombs, and pirs. These are also a clear example of the fact that the original inhabitants of this place were the Azerbaijani people. One of such religious and historical monuments is the tomb located in the village of Allahverdiyevli, dating back to the 5th-6th centuries. This village was part of the Chukhursad beylerbeyli during the Safavid period. From the information provided by I. Shopen, it is clear that it was included in the administrative territory of the Goycha district (Shopen, 1857, p.301). The tomb located in this village was intact until the final stage of deportation in 1987-1991. One of the ancient tombs is the tomb located in the village of Efendi, Yeni Bayazid district, Iravan province. This tomb dates back to the 3rd-2nd centuries (Alakbarli A., & Valiyev A., 2021, v.II p.22). Architecturally reminiscent of Zoroastrian temples, the tombs testify to the ancient historical traditions of our people. Among such tombs, one can also mention the tomb of Mir Hamza Nigari, built in the 19th century, and the tombs of Sheikh Ismail Sirajeddin. There are also various shrines and pilgrimage sites in the territory of Western Azerbaijan. One of them is the Ağag shrine, located in the village of Avdibay in the Iravan region (Alakbarli A., & Valiyev A., 2021, v.II p.100). It is known from historical sources and folklore that the tree cult belongs to the Turks. There are shrines associated with the tree cult in various Turkic peoples. Such shrines can also be found in other areas of Azerbaijan. Armenian sources themselves write that the people living in these areas are the Garapapags, which means that the Garapapags are one of the Turkic peoples and lived in other areas of Azerbaijan as well.

One of the places of religious belief in Western Azerbaijan is the Mahbub Ojag, located near Ellerkend in Amasya. The sources also mention that the Mahbub Ojag is one of the sacred places of the population of Aghbaba district. The population would visit it from time to time. (Alakbarli A., & Valiyev A., 2021, v.II

p.26). This religious-historical monument was also preserved until the final deportation of Azerbaijanis. Now it is not possible to obtain accurate information about the condition of Abda. Near the village of Qaranlig near Iravan, there was an Abdulsar hearth dating back to the 18th-19th centuries. Various graves dating back to ancient times also existed around this religious and architectural monument. One of the religious shrines was the Baba Haji shrine dating back to the 12th-13th centuries. This religious monument, located in the village of Nuvedi, was partially restored in 1960 as a result of the efforts of the village community. This shrine was destroyed after the deportation of Azerbaijanis in 1988-1991 (Alakbarli A., & Valiyev A., 2021, v.II p.35). These religious monuments once again show that these territories belong to Azerbaijanis. Therefore, most of them were destroyed by Armenians, and they are trying to pass off ancient Albanian temples as Armenian monuments by making artificial changes to them. However, religious features also expose these Armenian lies. Because Armenians are Gregorian as a religious sect, the cross they use is different from the ancient Albanian-Christian crosses.

J. Chardin, who was in Iravan in 1673, also reported on the mosque here. He wrote that there is a mosque opposite the city bazaar, which was named Div Sultan in honor of its builder. Div Sultan Rumlu was the Beylerbey of Iravan from 1515. It seems that he had the mosque built (Chardin, J., 1994, p.22). It should be noted that according to the Turkmenchay Treaty of 1828, the territories we are talking about came under the control of Tsarist Russia. According to Article XV of that treaty, Armenians began to be resettled to these territories. Some of the historical monuments here, including mosques, were used for other purposes and underwent certain changes. This is also evidenced by the information provided by the German researcher August Haksthausen. Thus, August Haksthausen visited the city of Iravan in August 1843. While there, he provided information about the two mosques in the Iravan fortress, and wrote that the Rajab Pasha Mosque was turned into a Russian-Greek church, and the Sardar Mosque into an armory (Mustafa N., 2016, p.18).

In the "Memory Booklet of Iravan Governorate for 1902", it is written that there were 310 mosques in Iravan Governorate that year. This document notes that 7 mosques were located in Iravan city (Mustafa N., 2016, p.14). Information about mosques in Iravan city can also be found in the works of Armenian researchers. Among them, M. Gasparyan wrote about the existence of the Blue Mosque, Haji Huseyn and Shahar (Zal Khan) mosques, Tepebashi Mosque, Haji Novruzali Bey, Haji Jafar Bey and Demirbulag mosques in Iravan in the late 19th and early 20th centuries. (Gasparyan, M.A., 1979, p.66) Information about the mosques in Iravan can also be found in the documents of the Imperial Archaeological Commission. According to the decision of the commission, in 1911, academician Nikolai Marr visited the Iravan Khan's Palace and got acquainted with the situation there. In his report to the meeting of the Imperial Archaeological Commission on May 17,

1912, Nikolai Marr described the Abbas Mirza Mosque and wrote: "The mosque is still in good condition, but no measures are being taken to preserve it, and everything serves to bring the Sardar Palace to its current state. However, it is a valuable heritage of local Muslim culture: inside the dome there is an inscription in Arabic letters around its circumference; the patterns on the mihrab resemble carpets and are highly stylized. The dome has cracks and has long been in need of repair" (Izvestiya Imperatorskoy Arkheologicheskoy Komissii, 1912, p. 79).

It should be noted that, according to statistical data, in 1915, there were 391 mosques in the territories included in the Iravan and Zangezur governorates. However, after the establishment of the Armenian state - starting in 1918, the destruction of mosques began and most of them were completely destroyed. Thus, in 1924, a plan was approved for the reconstruction of the city of Iravan. Ancient historical monuments belonging to the Azerbaijani people were destroyed and new residential buildings, etc. were built in their place. This was also noted by the Armenian author M.A. Gasparyan, who conducted research on the renovation of the architectural structure in Iravan at the beginning of the 20th century. In his dissertation "Architecture of Residential Buildings in Yerevan at the Beginning of the 19th-20th Centuries," which he defended in 1983, Gasparyan wrote that one of the main goals of the changes made was to "substantiate national characteristics" in the architecture, constructions, and decorative-artistic decoration of the mentioned buildings. The author also emphasized that in 1975, the Yerevan Department of Architectural Monuments was organized within the Main Architecture and Planning Department of the Iravan City Council Executive Committee. This contributed to Armenia "adding" national features to its monuments (Gasparyan, M.A., 1983, p.12).

On October 6, 2003, the Minister of Foreign Affairs of the Republic of Armenia, Vardan Oskanyan, stated at a press conference that there were only 3 mosques. However, the above facts, as well as the information written by Armenian researchers at the time, show that the minister tried to falsify history. Nevertheless, Oskanyan admitted that one of the mosques was demolished in 1930 (Mustafa N., 2016, p.16). One of the Minister's confessions was that the Blue Mosque is the oldest building in Yerevan and that the Armenian churches built one after the other only took place after the occupation of Yerevan by Russian troops in the 19th century. In 2007, the Armenian government submitted to the Council of Europe a list of temples and historical monuments belonging to religious and national minorities in the country and protected by the Armenian government. In the mentioned list, the Blue Mosque is presented as an Iranian mosque (Mustafa, N., 2024, p.2365; European Charter for Regional or Minority Languages, 2007).

The Armenian government and Armenians have destroyed a significant part of the material and cultural monuments belonging to the Azerbaijani people, and have tried to falsify and alter some of them. In this regard, international organizations should conduct

monitoring in this area, and the armenian government should report on the fate of the monuments found in sources and written documents. For comparison, let us note that the armenian church in Baku, which was built by the Azerbaijani state and the tolerant Azerbaijani people, is still being preserved and preserved today. This historical and religious monument, called the Church of St. Gregory the Illuminator or the Baku Armenian Church, is currently located at 27 Nigar Rafibeyli Street in Baku. By the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Azerbaijan No. 132 dated August 2, 2001, it was included in the list of "National Register of Historical Monuments in Azerbaijan" as an immovable historical and cultural monument of local importance (inventory number No. 3272) (Decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Azerbaijan № 132 dated August 2, 2001). On April 26, 2010, Catholicos of All Armenians Karekin II and the clergy accompanying him visited the church (Mammadov C., 2020). Also, in 2020, a visit of French MPs to the church took place (French MPs visit Armenian Church in Baku, 2020).

Result. The monuments existing in the territory of Western Azerbaijan, as well as the archaeological materials obtained, reflect historical truths. The history, etymological features of these monuments, and the topography of the area where they are located clearly show this. It is also clear from the descriptions and inscriptions reflected on the historical monuments that these monuments belong to the Azerbaijani people. In addition, certain information about these monuments is reflected in various written sources - in the diaries of European travelers, historical documents, and official statistical collections of Tsarist Russia. When both the material and cultural samples and the information in the written sources in which they are described are analyzed in a complex manner, the historical reality becomes clear. The result obtained shows that the author of the material and cultural samples located in Western Azerbaijan is the Azerbaijani people. A significant part of these monuments has been destroyed and subjected to various changes. However, these sources and written sources prove that the territory of Western Azerbaijan is the historical land of the Azerbaijani people.

References

1. Alakbarli, A. Monuments of Western Azerbaijan. Baku, 2007, 272 p.
2. Alakbarli A., & Valiyev A., (2021) Tarixi Azerbaijan torpaqlarında maddi-medeni irsimiz, Baku. SRC, v.I.233 p. [Ələkbərli Ə., Vəliyev Ə. Tarixi Azərbaycan torpaqlarında maddi-mədəni irsimiz, Bakı, 2021, 233 s.]
3. Alakbarli A., & Valiyev A., (2021) Garbi Azerbaijanaya gayidish: Tarixi Azerbaijan torpaqlarında maddi-medeni irsimiz, Baku. SRC, v.II.202 p. [Ələkbərli Ə., Vəliyev Ə. Tarixi Azərbaycan torpaqlarında maddi-mədəni irsimiz, Bakı, 2021, 233 s.]
4. Bayramov, I. (2023) Qadim Azerbaijan sheheri – İravan [Bayramov, I. Qədim Azərbaycan şəhəri – İrəvan. Ankara:, 210 s.]
5. Chardin J. (1994) Seyahetname [Şardən J. Səyahətnamə. Bakı: Elm, 1994, 96 s.]
6. Decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Azerbaijan № 132 dated August 2, 2001 URL: <https://e-qanun.az/framework/2847>
7. Evliya Chelebi seyahetnamesinde Azerbaijan (2012) Baku, 291 p. [Evliya Çələbi səyahətnaməsində Azərbaycan, (2012) Bakı, Nurlar NPM, 291 s.]
8. European Charter for Regional or Minority Languages URL: https://www.coe.int/t/dg4/education/minlang/report/PeriodicalReports/ArmeniaPR2_en.pdf
9. French MPs visit Armenian Church in Baku (2020) URL: <https://en.apa.az/foreign-policy/French-MPs-visit-Armenian-Church-in-Baku-coloredPHOTOcolor-335515>
10. Gasparyan, M. A. Arxitektura jilix domov Erevana XIX-nachala XX vv. Moskva, 226 p. [Гаспарян, М. А. Архитектура жилых домов Еревана XIX - начала XX вв. Москва, 226 с.]
11. Gasparyan, M.A. (1979) Planirovaniya struktura Erevana 19-nachala 20 vv. Natsionalnoe svoeobrazie zodchestva narodov SSSR. Moskva, p.64-72 [Гаспарян М.А. (1979) Планировочная структура Еревана 19-начала 20 вв. // Национальное своеобразие зодчества народов СССР. Москва, 1979, с. 64–72]
12. Huseynova, S. (8 Janary, 2014) Azerbaijanda memarlig ve arkheoloji abidelerin oyrenilmesi. [Hüseynova, S. (8 yanvar, 2014) Azərbaycanda memarlıq və arxeoloji abidələrin öyrənilməsi. *Mədəniyyət qəzeti*, S. 12.]
13. URL: <https://www.anl.az/down/meqale/medeniyyet/2014/yanvar/345152.htm>
14. Izvestiya Imperatorskoy Arkheologicheskoy Komissii. (1912) Vıpusk 46. S.Peterburg [Известия Императорской Археологической Комиссии. Выпуск 46. Санкт–Петербург, 1912, 148 с.]
15. ICOMOS international council on monuments and sites URL: <https://www.icomos.org/en>
16. Kariyev, E.M. & Samratova D.B. (2021) Pamyatniki arxeologii kak istoricheskiy istochnik: istoriograficheskiy obzor L.N.Gumilev atindaghi Euraziya ultigh universtitetinın xabarshisi. Tarixi gilimdar. Philosophiya. dinytanu seriyasi. № 1(134), с.63-80 [Кариев, Е.М. & Самратова Д.Б. (2021) Памятники археологии как исторический источник: историографический обзор Л.Н. Гумилев атындағы Еуразия ұлттық университетінің хабаршысы. Тарихи ғылымдар. Философия. Дінтану сериясы № 1(134), с.63-80 DOI: <https://doi.org/10.32523/2616-7255-2021-134-1-63-80>
17. Kalankatuklu, M. (2006) Albaniya tarixi, baku, 296 p. [Kalankatuklu, M. (2006) Albaniya tarixi Bakı, 296 s.]
18. Mammadov C. (2020) Bakida erməni kilsəsi [Məmmədov C. (2020) Bakıda erməni kilsəsi] URL: <https://www.anl.az/down/meqale/525/2020/noyabr/744391.htm>
19. Mustafa, N. (2024) İrəvan Şəhərində İslam İrsinə Qarşı Erməni Vandalizmi. Akademik Tarih ve

Düşünce Dergisi, 11 (4). 2361-2372.
<https://doi.org/10.46868/atdd.2024.711>

20. Mustafa, N. Y. (2020) İravan sheheri. Baku, [İrəvan şəhəri. Bakı - «Red N Line» MMC, 292 səh]

21. Mustafa, N. (2016) The Iravan knanate: Mosques of Iravan obliterated by Armenian vandals Baku, Public Society of Azerbaijan Historians. 44 p.

22. Musa, U. (2005) Zangezür [Musa, U. (2005) Zəngəzur. Bakı, "NURLAR" Nəqriyyat-Poliqrafiya Mərkəzi,. 504 s.]

23. Shopen, I. (1852) Istoricheskiy pamyatnik sostoyaniya Armyanskoy oblasti v epoxu eyo prisoedineniya k Rossiyskix imperii. St. Peterburg. [Шопен И. И. Исторический памятник состояния Армянской области в эпоху её присоединения к Российской империи. СПб., 1852, с.468.]

24. Sisian (spravochnik-putevoditel), (1987) [Сисиан (справочник-путеводитель), Ереван, 1987]